

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF CFRP-TO-CFRP JOINT STRUCTURE CONTAINING FIBER-METAL LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM), one of the damage mechanics approaches, offers some advantages over traditional fracture mechanics. The usage of CZM for progressive damage and failure modeling, the crack propagates along a predefined crack path, which greatly simplifies the modeling and calculation of the joint structure. In this study, the Fiber-metal laminates joint model based on CZM is presented based on the fracture behavior through experimental data. A parametric study was conducted with adhesive bonding specimen which containing CZM. Bonding length, steel thickness, and laminate sequence were selected as parameters. From the parametric study, it was investigated that the effect of selected parameters on mechanical strength and crack propagation behavior. The analytical results show good agreement with fracture behavior of joint specimen which observed by experiment. Also, optimal parameters were driven from the parametric study.

1 INTRODUCTION

Many researchers have been working on the design of FRP / steel joints for many years. Generally, two approaches are used for the design of adhesive joints: stress / strain based and energy based. The design method based on stress and strain states is that fracture occurs when the component associated with the joint exceeds a specific value such as material strength. Although this method is very simple, there are many uncertainties in the design of adhesive joints due to complex properties such as stress singularity, stress concentration, and stress distribution [1, 2]. The use of energy-based methods is one of the solutions to uncertainty. However, the main problem of this method is that provides a data correction scheme rather than a predictive capability because the physics of fatigue crack growth could not be obtained. Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM), one of the damage mechanics approaches, offers some advantages over traditional fracture mechanics [3]. The usage of CZM for progressive damage and failure modeling, the crack propagates along a predefined crack path, which greatly simplifies the modeling and calculation of the joint. However, it is still necessary to specify the position of the crack path, and it requires precisely measured properties to calculate the exact damage evolution of the model. In this study, the FML joint model based on CZM is presented based on the fracture behavior through experimental data. Further, a parametric study was carried out with the material thickness and lamination pattern as parameters so that the results could be used in the design of the structure.

2 DEVELOPMENT OF FML JOINT MODEL

2.1 Mechanical tests

The mechanical properties of CFRP and steel sheet were evaluated to use laminated composites for finite element analysis. The carbon fabric is an orthotropic material which has different properties in the longitudinal direction and transverse direction. The mechanical properties were obtained for both directions, and the specifications and experimental setup are shown in Table 5.1. Tensile, compressive and shear tests were carried out according to ASTM standards, and data corresponding to the input values of the CTL theory was derived from the test results. In order to accurately measure the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio, a two-axis rosette strain gage was used. The device was constructed as shown in 5.4. To collect the data, the DAC equipment MGC Plus (HBM, Germany) was used. The gages were attached perpendicularly to the test specimens, and the strain was recorded from each

gauge. Table 2 show the mechanical properties of CFRP and Mild steel which obtained through mechanical testing.

Type of test	Tensile test	Compressive test	Inter-lamina shear test
Standard	ASTM D3039	ASTM D695	ASTM D5379
Cross head speed	3 mm/min	1.3 mm/min	2 mm/min
Measured properties	Tensile strength, Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio	Compressive strength, Compressive modulus	Shear modulus

Table 1: Mechanical test setup and conditions [4-6]

Properties	Unit	CFRP Longitudinal	CFRP Transverse	Mild steel	Adhesive film
Tensile Strength, σ	MPa	2403.81	55.28	330 28(yield)	-
Young's Modulus, E	GPa	126.86	7.00	206	3.6
Poisson's Ratio, ν		0.31	-	0.30	0.3
Shear Modulus, G	GPa	4.73	-	76.92	0.03
Compressive Strength, σ_c	MPa	892.31	170.63	407.70	-
Compressive Modulus, E _c	GPa	7.20	1.51		-

Table 2: Mechanical properties.

2.2 Analytical model

The two CFRP plates below FML specimen, which has single strap design, are discontinuous, and stress is concentrated in the center of the joint. In addition, CFRP and Mild steel are bonded by adhesive, and the fracture behavior shows separation of CFRP and Mild steel as shown in Figure 1. In order to apply the fracture behavior, 'Cohesive zone model' and 'Separation-Distance based Debonding' were adopted to finite element analysis. In this property, it is possible to define the separation of adhesive layer according to change of contact stress and the slip distance. In this property, it is possible to define the separation of adhesive layer according to change of contact stress and the slip distance. A shallow elasticity element was added to an interface of the lower CFRP to improve the separation behavior of the two plates. Figure 2 shows tensile behavior of FML joint specimen model. From the analytical result, it can be seen that the deformation behavior shows good agreement with experimental results. Parametric studies were conducted to investigate the factors affecting the joint strength of the FML design. The length and width of the FML specimen are 250 and 25 mm respectively. The length of an adhesive layer is 60 mm, which is the same as FML joint specimens in experimental work. The upper steel sheet is bonded to lower two CFRP by 60 mm. On the other hand, bottom two CFRP plates are bonded to steel sheet by 30 mm respectively. The initial stacking order of carbon fibers was [0/90/90/0], and parametric studies were conducted to investigate the effect of joining parameters which are related to joining length, stacking order and adhesive thickness. Table 3 shows the properties of a cohesive zone to simulate fracture at the joint.

Figure 1: Fracture behavior of FML joint specimens.

Figure 2: Tensile behavior of FML model.

Properties	Value
Debonding interface mode	Mode II
Maximum Normal Contact Stress	200
Contact Gap at the Completion of Debonding	0.1
Maximum Equivalent Tangential Contact Stress	100
Tangential Slip at the Completion of Debonding	0.3
Artificial Damping Coefficient	3

Table 3: Defined 'Separation-Distance based Debonding' properties

2.3 Verification of FE model

Figure 3 shows preliminary analysis results using FMLs model. In case of deformation behavior, the crack propagates from middle point to left side edge along with adhesive layer, which is located under steel sheet layer. Left side in FMLs model is that cohesive zone is inserted between the steel sheet and adhesive film. From the Figure 3(a), It can be seen that the deformation behavior shows good agreement with experimental results.

When a tensile load is applied to the model, the crack progresses along the joint surface to reach the final fracture, where the highest stress appears near the crack path. Most stresses appear at the interface with two lower CFRP plates, and very low stresses in the upper CFRP plate and steel layers. The lower CFRP are stacked in the order of [0/90/90/0], and it can be seen that the stress is concentrated on the first (bottom) and fourth (top) layers arranged in the 0° direction.

Therefore, the FML design is expected to have higher strength when it is optimized that the parameters affecting the stress distribution around the joint, such as bonding length of the adhesive layer, the thickness of the material, and the laminate sequence of carbon fabric.

(a) Deformation behavior with time

(b) Stress distribution and crack propagation behavior on adhesive layer

Figure 3: Tensile behavior of FML model.

2.4 Parametric study for improvement of joint design

Parametric studies were conducted to investigate the factors affecting the joint strength of the FML design. The mechanical properties of the materials are shown in Table 4. The length and width of the FML specimen are 250 and 25 mm respectively. The length of an adhesive layer is 60 mm, which is the same as FML joint specimens in experimental work. The upper steel sheet is bonded to lower two CFRP by 60 mm. On the other hand, bottom two CFRP plates are bonded to steel sheet by 30 mm respectively. The initial stacking order of carbon fibers was [0/90/90/0], and parametric studies were conducted to investigate the effect of joining parameters which are related to joining length, stacking order and adhesive thickness.

	CFRP	Mild steel	Adhesive film
Ex	126.86	206.00(isotropic)	3.60 (isotropic)
Ey	7.0		
G12	4.73	76.92	0.03
v12	0.31	0.30	0.30

Table 4: Mechanical properties for FE analysis

For the comparison of the analysis results, the stress measurement points were divided into 6 points as shown in Figure 4, and the stresses at the joints were compared according to the joining parameters. The measurement point was selected from 'node A' to node 'F', which are located on the surface of the lower CFRP.

Figure 4: The location of the stress measurement.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Steel thickness effect

Stresses value on CFRP was picked from outer one layer, which is adjacent to the adhesive layer. In case of CFRP, the highest stress is generated near crack tip, and the stresses decrease with far away from the crack tip. After, the stress increases again at the point A, which is the end of the joint. Similarly, steel sheet showed the highest stress at the crack tip, but the stress became closer to zero toward the end of the joint. The stresses near the crack tip produced by bending force represent the tensile (red color) and compressive (blue color) stress, which show a significant difference. Although there is a high-stress difference between the CFRP and the steel sheet at the end of joint, there is no further crack initiation at point A, which is the end of the joint, because the stress generated at the crack tip is much higher.

The effect of thickness shown in Figure 5, explains that CFRP has higher stress than thin steel sheet. However, the stress on CFRP is decreased with increasing the steel thickness. It is analyzed that the thicker the steel sheet, the smaller the bending deformation and the less stress is at the crack tip. On the other hand, since the CFRP receives the stress dispersed by the steel sheet, the CFRP stress significantly increases. Among three different steel thickness, 0.6t steel sheet shows the lowest stress where near the crack tip (E), and the optimum thickness at which the joint specimen has the lowest stress is expected to be between 0.5 and 0.6. These behaviors mean that the properties on the adhesive layer can be controlled by using the steel thickness as design parameters.

Figure 5: Stress distribution on joint area with different steel thickness.

3.2 Adhesion length effect

Figure 6 shows the stress distribution along with changes in joining length, and the behavior of stress distribution is the same as the case of Fig. 5.19. First, the maximum stresses in the CFRPs were decreased to 812, 784, and 744 MPa, respectively, depending on the bond lengths. The steel sheets showed increasing behavior at 821, 885, and 946 MPa, respectively. The stress in the CFRP was increased when the bond length was short, and the stress in the steel sheet was increased when the bond length was long. These behavior show that if the bond length is too short, stress concentrates on the CFRP.

Figure 6: Stress distribution on joint area with different joint length.

3.3 Laminate sequence effect

Figure 7 shows the stress behavior with different lamination types of CFRP plate. It is composed of four carbon fiber layers. The outside is fixed at 0° and fiber orientations of two inner layers are increasing gradually in with Type I (90°), Type II ($\pm 45^\circ$), Type III, ($\pm 30^\circ$). When the orientation of the carbon fiber is changed, the stiffness of the laminates also changes. This behavior is due to the difference in mechanical properties at the joint surface, and the stress distribution caused by tensile load also changes. According to the calculation results with the classical laminate theory, the modulus of elasticity in the direction of crack growth gradually increased to 73.97, 78.28, and 92.09 GPa, respectively, and the stress at the crack tip gradually increased in proportion to the stacking type. However, torsional deformation occurred under tensile loading due to the asymmetry of the CFRP stacking sequence. Symmetric and asymmetric laminated joint model were used for analysis as shown in Fig. 5.22. The results of the analysis indicate that the stresses are appearing on steel sheet surface of joint. The analytical results show that even though the stiffness of the CFRP plate is the same, the stress generated at the tip of the crack is different. In case of the symmetric laminated structure, the stress is lower.

Figure 7: Stress distribution on joint area with different laminate sequence.

3.4 Verification of FML model with circular joint tube analysis

Developed FML model was verified using circular tube model, which is one of a candidate to fabricate as an actual product. Finite element model for FML joint tube is shown in Figure 8. The length and diameters of tube model are 2 m and 0.2 m respectively. Single strap joint design was adopted, and laminate sequence of CFRP is $[0/0/60/-60/45/-45/45/-45]$. Mild steel sheet was inserted between upper and lower CFRP layer. The model shows good appearance because the protrusion is facing inward. One end face was fixed, and remote displacement was applied to opposite end face for producing bending stress on FML joint area. The cohesive zone was inserted between the steel sheet and lower adhesive layer as shown in the figure. Figure 8 show the results of FE analysis. A relatively low stress is distributed in the joint region because the thickness of the joint is thicker than that of the non-joint portion (Figure 8(a)). From the stress distribution on joint area, it is found that stress behavior is same as general single strap joint specimen. Crack initiation and propagation behavior also observed from cross section of joint area shown in Figure 8(c). Crack is produced on middle of joint, and propagated through adhesive layer.

Figure 8: Stress distribution on CFRP joint tube under external loading, (a) Overall (b) Joint area and (c) Cross section view

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, finite element FML model suggested, which include crack initiation and propagation behavior. Cohesive zone model is applied to FML model to simulate cracking behavior following the same experimental behavior. The conclusions are as follows.

Simulation results using FML model which is as same as the specimen used in experimental work shows good agreement with mechanical test results in single strap joint specimen level. Especially, the model is developed with commercial software ANSYS Workbench 18.0, which enable to apply to actual product more conveniently. From the parametric study, it was investigated that the effect of parameters selected as bonding length, steel thickness, and laminate sequence. The results show that these parameters were affected by adhesive strength, and further simulation work can obtain optimized parameters for improving the structural safety.

Finally, The CFRP tube joint structure which including FML model was simulated, and the results show good agreement with specimen level simulation. It is expected that developing the large-scale assembly structure using FML model is for cost reduction. The existing uni-body structure is one of candidates for replacing with assembly structure using developed model.

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